

ANALYSIS OF BUSINESS MANAGEMENT FUNCTIONS IN IT OUTSOURCING

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada IT-outsorsing asosiy mazmuni, afzallik va kamchiliklari, zamonaviy biznes jarayonlaridagi o'rni hamda korxonalar uchun samaradorlikka ta'siri haqida so'z yuritiladi. IT xizmatlarini tashqi mutaxassislariga topshirishning iqtisodiy va texnologik jihatlari tahlil qilindi.

Kalit so'zlar: IT-outsorsing, axborot texnologiyalari, biznes jarayonlari, dasturiy ta'minot, xavfsizlik, xizmat ko'rsatish, raqamlashtirish, IT-infratuzilma.

Аннотация. В этой статье рассматривается основное содержание, преимущества и недостатки ИТ-аутсорсинга, его роль в современных бизнес-процессах и его влияние на производительность предприятий. Проанализированы экономические и технологические аспекты передачи ИТ-услуг внешним специалистам.

Ключевые слова: ИТ-аутсорсинг, информационные технологии, бизнес-процессы, программное обеспечение, безопасность, сервис, цифровизация, ИТ-инфраструктура.

Annotation. This article examines the main content, advantages, and disadvantages of IT outsourcing, its role in modern business processes, and its impact on enterprise productivity. It also analyzes the economic and technological aspects of outsourcing IT services to external specialists.

Keywords: IT outsourcing, information technology, business processes, software, security, service, digitization, IT infrastructure.

ENTRANCE

IT outsourcing is the process by which a company transfers some or all of its IT functions (software development, infrastructure management, technical support, cybersecurity, testing and monitoring, cloud services, etc.) to external suppliers or providers. In the context of the transformation of the digital economy, most enterprises and organizations rely on information technology to effectively conduct their activities. However, the formation of an internal IT department, hiring qualified specialists, their continuous training, and updating IT infrastructure require a lot of resources and funds. Therefore, many companies are resorting to the practice of outsourcing IT services to specialized external organizations. In recent years, enterprises have preferred to turn to external specialized outsourcing companies rather than expanding internal IT resources to accelerate digital transformation. SI, cloud infrastructures, cybersecurity, and modern technologies - all of these are increasing the demand for IT outsourcing, and IT outsourcing is being viewed as a strategic investment.

IT outsourcing is the process of outsourcing information technology-related tasks such as software development, technical support, server management, and cybersecurity to external

specialists or companies. Through this model, organizations are able to focus more on their core business. Multi-sourcing is a model of using multiple providers in parallel.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Analysis of scientific and practical sources on IT outsourcing shows that in recent years this area has been viewed not only as a form of technical services, but also as a model of strategic cooperation. In the research of Quinn and Hilmer, the main goal of outsourcing is explained as cost reduction, efficient allocation of resources and simplification of internal processes. Lacity and Willcocks point to outsourcing as a catalyst for digital transformation processes [1].

Published research since the 2020s highlights several important trends. Deloitte reports list the following as key drivers of IT outsourcing:

- expansion of cloud infrastructure services;
- increasing demand for cybersecurity outsourcing;
- Automated technical services using SI;

Many domestic scientists are also conducting research on outsourcing services. Professor Mahkamov studied the role of mobile services in the development of the services market and their impact as a factor on the development of outsourcing services. Also, Associate Professor Ismoilova, Professor Mahkamov and Researcher Makhmudov studied the impact of the development of IT outsourcing on the development of e-commerce and analyzed that the development of services directly affects the development of infrastructure [2].

DISCUSSION AND ANALYSIS

While outsourcing was previously used primarily for technical support, businesses are now seeing it as the core of their digital transformation strategy. This is evident in areas such as IS, cloud infrastructure, DevOps, and cybersecurity, increasing the strategic importance of IT outsourcing.

Security is a key driver of demand for outsourcing. The rise in cyber threats is forcing enterprises to turn to specialized companies. Outsourcing providers provide real-time monitoring, security auditing, vulnerability detection, and security protection services. Therefore, cybersecurity outsourcing remains the fastest growing segment in 2024-2025[3].

Companies are working with multiple IT providers to avoid becoming dependent on a single provider. In addition, cooperation with service providers in geographically close areas (nearshore) is increasing.

In recent years, Uzbekistan has seen a surge in IT outsourcing exports - particularly in software development, call center services, and cybersecurity services. The increasing number of IT Park residents also indicates that the outsourcing market is growing rapidly [4].

Table 1

Theoretical characteristics, practical advantages and disadvantages of approaches to outsourcing services

Theoretical characteristics of outsourcing	Practical advantages and disadvantages of the approach
Functional approach	
The specific features of the approach are the study of outsourcing as a means of implementing key management functions (from planning and, at the very least, control) focused on various areas of the client's activity, taking into account strategic goals and objectives.	

<i>Advantages: the ability to plan the results of the implementation of management functions; the introduction of progressive tools and methods for implementing management functions, etc.</i>	<i>Disadvantages: reducing the essence of outsourcing to management functions only; limiting the outsourcing methodology by the management cycle, etc.</i>
Approach to resources	
Within the framework of the approach, the goal of outsourcing services is to increase the efficiency of using available resources (financial, material, labor) based on optimizing (improving) various parameters and factors affecting the activities of the enterprise.	
<i>Advantages: the ability to develop an outsourcing methodology based on an analysis of obstacles in the “resources-costs-results” chain; development of the existing potential of the enterprise, etc.</i>	<i>Disadvantages: the need for a detailed analysis of available resources (including factor analysis) with the search for reserves and maximizing the efficiency of their use, etc.</i>
Approach to activity	
Outsourcing services are considered as a specific type or separate area of activity of a specialized organization to solve problems of the activity and development of an enterprise, the growth of its quantitative and qualitative results, the formation of strategic goals and operational tasks.	
<i>Advantages: the ability to provide a detailed and “targeted” solution to the existing problems of the enterprise, entities specializing in this area; the formation of an anti-crisis methodology for the activities of a specific client of outsourcing services, etc.</i>	<i>Disadvantages: focus on the organizational features of the activities of specialized enterprises, rather than on the methodological foundations of the provision of outsourcing services, etc.</i>
Process approach	
Outsourcing services are considered as a specific type or separate area of activity of a specialized organization to solve problems of the activity and development of an enterprise, the growth of its quantitative and qualitative results, the formation of strategic goals and operational tasks.	
<i>Advantages: maximum optimization or modernization of individual business processes; reducing costs for implementing business processes and increasing their efficiency, etc.</i>	<i>Disadvantages: risk of partial or complete loss of control over enterprise resources (material, labor, financial) or outsourced business processes.</i>
Collaborative approach	
Within this approach, outsourcing services act as a connecting link in the relationship between the provider and the client, simultaneously acquiring rights, obligations, and powers within the framework of a concluded contract or other documents.	
<i>Advantages: consideration of the process of providing outsourcing services from the perspective of the mutual obligations and rights of their vendors and customers; support of the outsourcing methodology with legal assistance, etc.</i>	<i>Disadvantages: the possibility of legal consequences for fulfilling/not fulfilling certain clauses of the contract, etc.</i>
Situational approach	

<p>Within the framework of the approach, outsourcing services are considered as a way to solve specific problems or conflict situations (organizational, technical, information) through the adaptation or development of methodological tools.</p>	
<p><i>Advantages: the ability to quickly and effectively resolve problematic or conflict situations to increase the efficiency of the enterprise, etc.</i></p>	<p><i>Disadvantages: the likelihood of formal performance of functional duties; the costs of resolving a problem or conflict situation may exceed the potential benefits.</i></p>

The main types of IT outsourcing can be classified as follows:

1. Software development outsourcing. Outsourcing is the process of outsourcing all or part of a company's programming, mobile applications, websites, CRM or ERP systems, testing, design, DevOps, integration, and support to a team of external professional programmers, without establishing its own IT team[5].

2. Technical support outsourcing. This is understood as the process of analyzing and resolving problems related to a company's IT systems, devices, programs, and networks, and users, performed by an external professional vendor instead of an internal IT department.

3. Infrastructure management outsourcing. The process of outsourcing operational processes related to a company's IT infrastructure (servers, networks, cloud, cyber, data center, storage and backup, monitoring, support, DevOps, etc.) to external professional service providers.

4. Cybersecurity outsourcing. Security monitoring, vulnerability assessment, security policy creation. It is the process of outsourcing an organization's security monitoring, threat detection/response, configuration and management, vulnerability scanning, penetration testing, threat intelligence, etc. to external vendors. This can be cost-effective in small and medium-sized businesses due to lack of internal expertise, resources, and cost [6].

In today's global competitive environment, IT outsourcing helps companies quickly adapt to market demands. It creates an opportunity for startups to grow rapidly, while large enterprises can optimize costs and improve service quality. Due to the increasing digitalization processes, the demand for IT outsourcing is increasing every year.

Digital transformation and migration to the cloud. Companies continue to migrate their infrastructure to the cloud, creating a significant opportunity for outsourcing providers to manage infrastructure and deliver cloud services. By leveraging the cloud model, companies are gaining greater flexibility and the ability to manage variable workloads [7].

These Internet services, also known as “cloud services,” can be divided into three main categories:

- infrastructure as a service (IaaS);
- platform as a service (PaaS);
- software as a service (SaaS).

Clouds can be public or private.

A private cloud is an infrastructure designed for use by a single organization, including multiple consumers (e.g., divisions of an organization).

Private cloud - owned and managed by the organization itself or by a third party, and can be physically located both within and outside the owner's jurisdiction.

A public cloud is an infrastructure that is available to the general public for free use. A public cloud can be owned and operated by commercial, academic, or government organizations. A public cloud is physically located in the jurisdiction of the owner—the service provider [8,9].

A hybrid cloud is a combination of two or more different cloud infrastructures that remain unique entities but are interconnected with standardized or proprietary technologies to transfer data and applications.

A public cloud is a type of infrastructure designed for use by a specific community of users of organizations with common tasks. A public cloud may be owned, operated, and managed by one or more public organizations or jointly, and may be physically located both within and outside the owner's jurisdiction.

Cybersecurity and risk management. As ransomware, data theft, and other cyber threats increase, companies are increasingly outsourcing their security processes to outside experts. Outsourcing providers are offering security monitoring, vulnerability assessment, and attack response services. The growing importance of cybersecurity outsourcing means that in-house IT departments are not always able to adequately cover such expertise.

Artificial intelligence (AI) and autonomous automation. SI and RPA - robotic process automation - are increasingly being used in outsourcing services. On the one hand, this increases efficiency (coding, testing, automation of simple administrative tasks), and on the other hand, it leads to structural changes in the labor market. After the introduction of artificial intelligence, the concept of “transformational outsourcing” began to be widely used in the literature - in which the outsourcing strategy is aimed at implementing technology, reengineering business processes, and optimizing the resulting KPIs.

Transformational outsourcing (strategic partnership). In the traditional outsourcing model, external companies only perform services, but in the modern “transformational outsourcing” model, they act as strategic partners and help the enterprise implement new technologies and innovations. This model helps enterprises remain competitive and adapt to digital transformation.

The proposed definition of the concept of outsourcing focuses on management functions and business processes. At the same time, the classic example of management functions was those proposed by M. Mescon: planning, organization, motivation, control. These management functions are implemented within the framework of outsourcing services and the proposed definition is detailed as follows [10, 11]:

Table 2

Planning the tasks of management functions in outsourcing services

Planning	Within the framework of this function, the goals and objectives of the outsourcing services customer are determined, and appropriate mechanisms are developed to implement approved strategic plans;
Organization	with the help of outsourcing services, a certain range of tasks related to the organization of their client's activities is solved (from the development and improvement of elements of the organizational structure to the optimization of job responsibilities);
Encouragement	The implementation of the function is aimed at developing activities, and the implementation of incentives and controls contributes to the effective, well-coordinated activities of employees for the clients of outsourcing services;
Control	Within the framework of outsourcing services, their client and the “seller” jointly monitor the process of achieving the set goals, identify any deviations from the planned ones, and promptly correct further actions.

It is not difficult to see that all of the above functions together represent a closed management cycle, in which each of them complements and expands the capabilities of the other. Moreover, often such a set of functions is associated with one or another “autonomous” business process. At the same time, we note that outsourcing itself can act as a separate business process, or it can be understood as a sequence of actions logically connected with a business process [12].

Conclusion. IT outsourcing is an integral part of modern business, helping organizations achieve cost-effectiveness, innovation and high efficiency. The right outsourcing company accelerates the technological development of the organization and increases its competitiveness. Therefore, IT outsourcing is a strategically important decision. IT outsourcing today is not only a means of reducing costs, but also an important element of strategic digital transformation. Outsourcing providers are expanding in areas such as cloud infrastructure, cybersecurity, IS and automation. At the same time, IS is changing the structures of the labor market and increasing risks - this requires employees and companies to adapt to change.

If a few years ago outsourcing services were used only by the private sector, today the use of these services is being widely implemented in state-owned enterprises and is yielding positive results. This made it possible to substantiate the proposed definition of the concept of “outsourcing”, as a result of which the types and forms of modern outsourcing services were discussed. The results of the study of the theoretical foundations of outsourcing services in modern conditions served as the basis for the development of a composite model that harmoniously combines the main forms, types and approaches to understanding the essence of outsourcing.

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